

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

H2020-IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020

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Deliverable

Reference number and title:

Deliverable 7.4 Documentation of dissemination of project results

Name of lead beneficiary:

University of Copenhagen

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Dissemination level: Public

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Description of the deliverable

Deliverable title: **D 7.4 DOCUMENTATION OF DISSEMINATION OF PROJECT RESULTS**

Work Package: WP 7 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication [Month 1-36] led by University of Copenhagen

D7.4 Documentation of dissemination of project results provides an overview of dissemination and communication activities in TRAIN4EU during its full project period from January 2021 to December 2023, as well as the pre-project period in 2020 when TRAIN4EU was awarded funding through Horizon2020. Focus is on dissemination efforts through four main channels: on-line and in-person events such as webinars and conferences, webpage, 4eu+ newsletter and social media. It concludes with some perspectives on dissemination pathways for project results post-project.

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TRAIN4EU dissemination

During the TRAIN4EU project, the aim has been to disseminate, exploit and communicate outcomes and learning across 4eu+ and other European University Alliances, as well as to inform and engage relevant internal and external stakeholders, to maximise impact. Dissemination activities are based on the plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC plan) articulated in D7.1 DEC plan (M6) with updates D7.2 (M24) and D7.3 (M35). The main dissemination activities have been to:

- Create a DEC Plan with updates
The DEC Plan has been updated twice as the project develops; please see below for details.
- Map main stakeholders.
To focus communication and use the limited resources constructively, relevant stakeholders have been identified, categorized and mapped in the DEC Plan – ordered after each stakeholder’s influence on and interest in the project; see D7.3 (M35).
- Prioritize target groups
The target groups have been listed in order of priority in the DEC Plan. For every action in the plan which target groups should be in focus has been considered; see D7.3 (M35).
- Maintain and optimize webpage
There has been a focus on the web performance of the webpage, especially to search engine optimize and to communicate main messages about TRAIN4EU clearly to the target groups.
- Create content
Based on input from WPs, content have been created and published on relevant channels and in cooperation with the 4eu+ Comms team. Content has been published on existing 4eu+ digital infrastructure channels such as web, newsletter and social media.
- Document dissemination
This report D7.4 is part of the documentation of dissemination activities; please also see D7.5 Publications on lessons learned and best practices (M36) for further information.

The plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) of TRAIN4EU activities and outcomes has been a work in progress, developed and adjusted as TRAIN4EU progressed. The draft TRAIN4EU DEC plan D7.1 (M6) and the tentative implementation plan (annex I) have been through several revisions as new opportunities and insights have arisen during the project's lifetime. The planned and implemented DEC activities were developed, adjusted and carried out in an ongoing co-creative and transparent process between the Alliance partners and in dialogue with internal and external stakeholders to ensure that TRAIN4EU activities and outcomes are disseminated widely to maximise impact. The DEC Plan has been developed and adjusted through three versions:

- D7.1 DEC plan (M6)
- D7.2 DEC plan 1st update (M24)
- D7.3 DEC plan 2nd update (M35)

The current report provides an overview of TRAIN4EU dissemination and communication for the full project period January 2021 to December 2023. Content based on activities and outcomes from WP1-6 are outlined to provide a status over dissemination efforts as TRAIN4EU comes to an end.

To ensure transparency, involvement, and co-ownership between WP7 and WP1-6, as well as timely and frequent reporting to and collaboration with WP6, WP8 and the Steering Committee, all mass communication results are monitored in a scheme that also serves as a reporting schedule. The activities are categorized according to DEC channels and scheduled in chronological order below.

TRAIN4EU dissemination channels

Events

On-line and in-person events such as webinars, seminars, workshops, fora and conferences are a main channel for disseminating TRAIN4EU activities and outcomes. Most such events have been centered around TRAIN4EU / 4eu+ exchanges with other European University Alliances / SwafS projects. Documentation of dissemination of project results through the main events coordinated or co-organised by TRAIN4EU, listed below, are outlined under the webpage / newsletters / social media categories. They will only be briefly listed and described here to provide an overview.

- 2021: **TRAIN4EU kick-off meeting** on-line 13-14 January 2021.
 - Information can be found here: [Kick off of the TRAIN4EU project](#)
- 2022: **4eu+ infrastructure conference** on-line 8. June 2022
 - Information can be found here: [4EU+ Conference: Learnings, challenges and obstacles in educational and research infrastructure \(4euplus.eu\)](#)
- 2023: **TRAIN4EU Webinar on academia-society transfer** on-line 27. Nov. 2023
 - Information can be found here: [TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society \(4euplus.eu\)](#)
- 2023: **Swafs Cross-Alliances Forum** in Bruxelles 30. Nov.-1. Dec. 2023
 - Information can be found here: [SwafS conference: Science with and for Society in European University Alliances \(4euplus.eu\)](#)

For any on-line and in-person events where WP1-6 project members participated and disseminated project results beyond the main events listed, please refer to WP1-6 final reports D1.3-6.2 (M35).

Webpage

The TRAIN4EU webpages on the 4EU+ website are a vital source of information and gateway to the TRAIN4EU project for a broad audience with different backgrounds, interests and needs. Maintaining the website updated throughout the project and beyond is a central task for WP7.

In the REA Draft Project Review Report of TRAIN4EU Periodic Report 1 from 30. Sept. 2022, the following issues concerning the 4eu+ webpage were raised:

1. The TRAIN4EU logo to be used more prominently on all printed and digital materials related to the project, with the Horizon 2020 logo also clearly evident.
2. The possibility to find TRAIN4EU in a web search is not easy and possibly also adversely affected by its' positioning vis a vis 4EU+. Improving the web-text searchability should be addressed.

In response to the REA Draft Project Review Report, the following suggested ways to address the issues raised were sent to TRAIN4EU's project officer at REA on 21. Oct. 2022:

- Please note that TRAIN4EU does not have a separate project logo per se, but rather a visual identity centering on its acronym and associated with its deliverables.
- Every effort will be made in M19-36 to use TRAIN4EU's visual identity as well as the Horizon2020 logo more prominently in project related materials, particularly in relation to TRAIN4EU's digital presence.
- The emphasis on visual identity and logos will go hand in hand with a more focused effort to improve TRAIN4EU's web presence and searchability. Work addressing these dimensions is already being planned and carried out in WP7 as a result of the periodic review recommendations, including setting up a meeting in M23 (Nov. 2022) with the 4eu+ Communications group, based at University of Warsaw, PL.

The issue of including the Horizon2020 logo more prominently in project related materials was addressed immediately after the REA review meeting with TRAIN4EU on 9. Sept. 2022.

To strengthen web performance the following has been attempted, reflecting recommendations from the Periodic Review 1 (M1-18) REA report results and review meeting on 9. Sept. 2022:

- Pointing out main keywords to make it possible for people to find the site via search engine
- Creating more precise and relevant texts, as well as shorter web text
- SEO (search engine optimization): strong headlines, anchors (internal links to other parts of texts), strong external links, keywords in meta-texts (short relevant summary of the page)
- New structure, including two boxes for news & events and pilots & recommendations
- More visualized content with more photos

In addition to the ongoing improvements made to the web in general, the site is used to publish news, events and recommendations. Please refer to the [TRAIN4EU webpage](#) for concrete dissemination and communication content.

Newsletters

TRAIN4EU does not have its own newsletter but uses the 4eu+ alliance newsletter to disseminate its activities and outcomes. 4eu+ newsletters can be accessed here: [Newsletter \(4euplus.eu\)](#)

Februar 2021: Newsletter item on TRAIN4EU kick-off meeting 13-14 January 2021.

Launch of the **TRAIN4EU+** project

Funded by Horizon 2020 programme, **TRAIN4EU+** aims to support the research and innovation dimension of 4EU+ Alliance's cooperation. The project's online kick-off meeting was hosted by the **University of Copenhagen** (project's coordinating institution), **13-14 January 2021**. [Read more >>](#)

The news item can be accessed here: [Kick off of the TRAIN4EU project](#)

October 2021: Newsletter item on TRAIN4EU WP1-5 progress

4EU+ RESEARCH

All aboard! **TRAIN4EU** moves on

The SwafS project aimed at transforming the research & innovation support functions in 4EU+ Alliance has reached its first delivery – a protocol on baselining and analysis of best practices within the subject areas of a common research agenda, R&I human capital, research support infrastructure, link with business and citizens, and Open Science. [More >>](#)

The news item can be accessed here: [TRAIN4EU moves on](#)

June 2022: Newsletter item on TRAIN4EU infrastructure conference 8. June 2022

The 4EU+ online conference *Educational research and infrastructure. Collaboration in European University Alliances* is behind us! The event, organised within the framework of EUP and **TRAIN4EU**+ projects, brought together alliance representatives and practitioners from **UNA-EUROPA, EUGLOH, EPICUR, CIVIS and CHARM-EU**, as well as the speakers from the **European Commission**. They had a chance to share experiences and lessons learned on collaborations and management of infrastructure. Thank you to all the speakers and participants for sharing your knowledge and valuable insights!

The news item can be accessed here: [4EU+ Conference: Learnings, challenges and obstacles in educational and research infrastructure \(4euplus.eu\)](#)

February 2023: Newsletter item on TRAIN4EU support to entrepreneurship

16. 2. 2023

TRAIN4EU+ to support

entrepreneurship across the alliance

The news item can be accessed here: [TRAIN4EU+ to support entrepreneurship across the alliance \(4euplus.eu\)](#)

June 2023: Newsletter dedicated to TRAIN4EU

Special edition of the 4EU+ newsletter (June 2023)

The news item can be accessed here: [Taking a fast TRAIN to institutional R&I transformation \(4euplus.eu\)](#)

October 2023: Newsletter item promoting TRAIN4EU related events

TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society

The event, organised by the team of the TRAIN4EU+ Work Package 4: Linking citizens-academia-business (led by Sorbonne University), **will showcase the effectiveness of the link between academia and business** based on the experience of 4EU+'s collaboration with its socio-economic partners. The event will be held on 27 November, fully online.

[Read more >>](#)

R&I in European Universities Alliances – Cross-Alliances Forum 2023

Co-organised by 4EU+ in the framework of the **TRAIN4EU+ project**, the conference (30 November - 1 December, Brussels) will **present the results of completed and ongoing R&I projects within the European University Alliances**. Plenary sessions, round table discussions, workshops and keynote speeches by high-level European policy makers and academic stakeholders are planned. [Read more >>](#)

Notice promoting the TRAIN4EU+ Webinar organized by WP4 /SU: Transfer from academia to business and society on 27. Nov. 2023; the news item can be accessed here: [TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society \(4euplus.eu\)](#)

Notice promoting the Science with and for Society Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 in Bruxelles, co-organised by TRAIN4EU WP6 /UCPH on 30. Nov.-1. Dec. 2023; the news item can be accessed here: [SwafS conference: Science with and for Society in European University Alliances \(4euplus.eu\)](#)

December 2023: Newsletter item on TRAIN4EU WP4 webinar on transfer 27. Nov. 2023

TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society

On 27 November 2023, TRAIN4EU+ hosted a webinar entitled 'Transfer from academia to business and society'. The webinar, organized and hosted by Sorbonne University TRAIN4EU+ and 4EU+ local team, gathered high level representatives from 4EU+ member universities, European Commission officials, valuable socio-economic partners and more than 50 participants from across the

consortium.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016674.

The news item can be accessed here: [4EU+ News | December 2023 \(mailchi.mp\)](#)

December 2023: Newsletter item on SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 30.Nov.- 1.Dec. 2023

SwafS conference: Science with and for Society in European University Alliances

During the 1½ day SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 in Bruxelles on 30 November and 1 December 2023, European Commission officials met with members of the European University Alliances to discuss the future of the research & innovation dimension within university alliances in Europe and to showcase best practices and lessons learned from the Horizon2020-funded SwafS projects.

The news item can be accessed here: [4EU+ News | December 2023 \(mailchi.mp\)](#)

Social Media

An important assessment parameter and a benchmarking tool for European University alliances, social media performance plays a significant role for 4EU+ communication. X, Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram are all part of 4EU+ social media communication.

Based on the 4EU+ social media strategy and recent evaluations of how 4EU+ uses social media channels in terms of target groups and users, using the 4EU+ LinkedIn account is the obvious and preferable choice, which is why TRAIN4EU results have been communicated mainly on LinkedIn. For every event there have been posts on social media to attract an audience to webinars, conferences, meetings etc. See the chronological schedule below for links to specific posts.

During the two main transversal TRAIN4EU events ‘Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances’ and ‘Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances’ there have been live posts from the events on LinkedIn and X.

Please see the table below for social media posts pertaining to TRAIN4EU, arranged chronologically. The table includes all dissemination activities in TRAIN4EU for the project period January 2021 – December 2023, as well as the pre-project period in 2020, when TRAIN4EU received funding.

TRAIN4EU dissemination activities

Dissemination activities in 2020

Date	Channel	Reach	Link
July 2020	Web		News about TRAIN4EU+ project https://news.ku.dk/all_news/2020/07/eu-support-for-extended-university-collaboration/
July 2020	Web		News about TRAIN4EU+ project https://cppt.cuni.cz/CPPTNEN-129.html
July 2020	Web		News about TRAIN4EU+ project https://www.unimi.it/en/international/university-milan-world/university-milan-participates-4eu/4eu-research-and-innovation

Dissemination activities in 2021

Date	Channel	Reach	Link
February 2021	Newsletter	App. 700 followers	Launch of TRAIN4EU+ https://mailchi.mp/1f6fb7ec5c7d/4euplus-february2021
October 2021	X		TRAIN4EU+ Kickoff meeting and funding news https://x.com/UniKarlova/status/1288113803675045889?s=20
October 2021	X		TRAIN4EU+ Kickoff meeting and funding news https://x.com/LaStatale/status/1349331638514290689?s=20
October 2021	Web		TRAIN4EU+ Kickoff meeting and funding news https://en.uw.edu.pl/train4eu-project-awarded-h2020-funding/

Dissemination activities in 2022

Date	Channel	Reach	Link
5 May 2022	LinkedIn	851 followers	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6927950643106091008
5 May 2022	X	1370 follow. 7 retweets 13 likes	https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1522197391390265346
8 June 2022	X	1370 followers 21 likes 1 Quote 6 Retweets	(20) 4EUplusAlliance on Twitter: "🔔 Our #online Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration has just started! Together with representatives of @Una Europa, @eugloh19, @EpicurAlliance and @charm_eu we will share our experiences and lessons learned. 🌐 https://t.co/Q5ZZjGDPi6 https://t.co/35KA45HsxV " / Twitter
9 June 2022	Facebook	1465 followers	https://www.facebook.com/4EUplusAlliance/posts/1028579934695293

9 June 2022	X	1370 follow. 4 retweets 9 likes	https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1534795046389784576
9 June 2022	X		UNITECH as best practice https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1534795055852097536?s=20
9 June 2023	X		Reply about research infrastructure Anne Jürgens https://x.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1534795053822009344?s=20
9 June 2023	X		Reply about research infrastructure https://x.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1534795051762606081?s=20
9 June 2022	LinkedIn	851 followers	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6940602865262456832
9 June 2022	Instagram	1504 follow.	https://www.instagram.com/4euplus_alliance/
13 June 2022	X		Promotion for Inspiring Innovation, Culture and Developing Future-Proof Skills https://x.com/KratzIsabelle1/status/1539924013069246465?s=20
23 June 2022	4eu+ newsletter	775 subscribers, open rate: 41 %	Full follow-up article on the 4eu+ Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances News - 4EU+ Alliance (4euplus.eu)
23 June 2022	4eu+ newsletter	775 subscribers, open rate: 41 %	Highlight from the 4eu+ Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances: key take aways from the conference in Educational and Research Infrastructure European University Alliances 4EU+ Online Conference on Educational and Research infrastructure collaboration in European University Alliances - 4EU+ Alliance (4euplus.eu)
23 June 2022	4eu+ webpage		A featured page with key takeaways, questions and 4 videos https://4euplus.eu/4EU-368.html
10 October 2022	X		Reply from Anna Wolodko https://x.com/annawolodko/status/1579462597363265536?s=20
End of 2022	Web		HR Excellence in Research award renewal: Internal Review for Renewal Assessment https://en.uw.edu.pl/research/hr-excellence-in-research/

Dissemination activities in 2023

Date	Channel	Reach	Content/link
15 February 2023	Newsletter	1,104 subscribers, open rate: 41 %	Article about TRAIN4EU+ in Support of Academic Entrepreneurship https://us4.campaign-archive.com/?u=1e460ae8ee967656a42799a4d&id=feff68804c

February 2023	Web		Introducing TRAIN4EU at UCPH (updated version) Initiative to support research - KUnet
May 2023	LinkedIn		Report on the European Universities Alliances research projects https://www.linkedin.com/posts/czech-liaison-office-for-education-and-research-in-brussels_progress-of-university-alliance-projects-activity-7062023101802262529-9DK7/
1 June 2023	Newsletter	1118 subscribers Open rate 50,6%	Newsletter dedicated TRAIN4EU+ Taking a fast TRAIN to institutional R&I transformation (4euplus.eu)
11 August	X		Post about cases in research data and FAIR data, Responsible Publishing and Citizen Science https://x.com/karolinaminch/status/1689896019725590528?s=20
September 2023	Web		European Universities Initiative – a Policy of Scientific Cooperation on the Basis of Transform4Europe and The 4EU+ Alliance file:///C:/Users/caa/Downloads/European_Universities_Initiative_a_%20(1).pdf
12 October 2023	Newsletter	1,041 subsc., open rate: 52,8%	Promotion for TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from Academia to business and society https://4euplus.eu/4EU-415.html?newsID=19389
12 October 2023	Newsletter	1,041 subscribers, open rate: 52,8%	Promotion for conference: SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 R&I in European Universities Alliances- cross-alliances forum 2023 (4euplus.eu)
October 2023	LinkedIn		Promotion for TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from Academia to business and society https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135211681076408321/?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_feedUpdate%3A%28V%2Curn%3Ali%3Aaactivity%3A7135211681076408321%29
October 2023 + reminder repost November	X		Promotion for conference: SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1719312968863670359
October 2023 + reminder repost November	LinkedIn		Promotion for conference: SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125073024558465025
16 November 2023	X		Promotion for Train4EU+ webinar: Transfer from academia to Business and Society https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1725139521665224804?s=20
27 November 2023	Web		Promotion for Train4EU+ webinar: Transfer from academia to Business and Society https://sante.sorbonne-universite.fr/en/webinar-train4eu-transfer-academia-business-and-society

November 2023	LinkedIn		Citizenship, Multilingualism & Pluralities: Challenges & Opportunities for Europe in the 21st Century https://www.linkedin.com/posts/4euplus_4euplus-4euplusalliance-flagship2-activity-7135623679773687808-8a2C?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
November 2023	Web		Promotion for webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society (27 November) (4euplus.eu)
November 2023	Facebook		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://www.facebook.com/4EUplusAlliance/posts/pfbid0269AqZiZBKdvVjECgmUxJ3nqz51Hp1fSd2oRFo87upZD1awmP3iX2bh2ZwUYcwYyKl
November 2023	X		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1719312968863670359
November 2023	Facebook		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=851009023484614&set=pcb.851016733483843&locale=ar_AR
November 2023	LinkedIn		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125073024558465025/
November 2023	X		Post from General Assembly at Annual Meeting https://x.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1722286901778849973?s=20
November 2023	X		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1730140004318392652
November 2023	X		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1730513198804009041
November 2023	X		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://twitter.com/4EUplusAlliance/status/1730511460684517624

November 2023	Web		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://www.charm-eu.eu/science-and-society-european-universities-alliances-programme
November 2023	LinkedIn		Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://www.linkedin.com/posts/4euplus_european-universityalliances-swafsalliancesforum23-activity-7136347743924465665-nM3I?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
November 2023	Facebook		Promotion for Science with and for Society in European Universities Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 https://www.facebook.com/4EUplusAlliance/posts/pfbid0269AqZiZBKdvVjECgmUxJ3nqz51Hp1fSd2oRFo87upZD1awmP3iX2bh2ZwUYcwYyKl
December 2023	Newsletter	1,041 subscribers, open rate: 52,8%	Article about Cross-Alliance Forum 2023 – focus on TRAIN4EU+ https://4euplus.eu/4EU-415.html?newsID=19847

TRAIN4EU dissemination post-project

In terms of disseminating project results after the project ends, the aim is to ensure ongoing impact of TRAIN4EU outcomes and lessons learned. DEC pathways post-project include might include:

- further develop the TRAIN4EU webpage to have a sustainable afterlife
- communicate results and learnings to relevant internal and external stakeholders
- deposit TRAIN4EU deliverables in the generalist data repository Zenodo

As indicated in the TRAIN4EU Data Management Plan D8.8 (M6) and its first and second update D8.9 (M23) and D8.10 (M35), at project end, publicly shareable and non-confidential data in TRAIN4EU, along with their associated metadata and documentation, will be deposited in the generalist data repository [Zenodo](#). Zenodo is a free and open digital archive built by CERN and OpenAIRE and recommended and supported by the European Commission. It is a flexible and easy to use platform for making project data accessible, by enabling sharing of data in any size, format and from all fields of research, which in turn enables broad re-use and dissemination activities.

Data will be made available for re-use by third parties after project completion in December 2023. Deposited project data sets will be accessible for at least 10 years, the minimum guaranteed storage time for Zenodo. No embargo period for re-usable data is anticipated. Data sets deemed confidential or not relevant for use by third parties or public re-use will not be made available for re-use. Please see D8.10 Data Management Plan second update (M35) for further details.

